

Teaching and Learning Through Bakhtinian Lens

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Abstract

The principles developed by the philosopher Mikhail Bakhtin have positively impacted educational systems all over the globe once implemented. Yet, for a great majority of the American and international schools, Mikhail Bakhtin and his philosophical educational methods remain a novelty, if not an enigma. Bakhtin's followers and researchers (e.g., Boyd & Markarian, 2011; 2015; Caughlan et al., 2013; Fecho & Botzakis, 2007; Gould, 2018; Haneda & Wells, 2010; Nystrand, 2006) have been actively promoting this highly beneficial for both teaching and learning approach. The purpose of this theoretical paper presentation is to deliver to the wide international academic audiences the ideas on the multiple benefits from the Bakhtin's theories to practical teaching. In the basis of the phenomenon of a dialogic education, there rests the Greek word *διαλογικός* or "dialogic." According to such researchers as Penlington (2011) and Stahl (2006), this term consists of two salient parts, which can be translated from the Greek language as *dual* (dia) and *logical* (logic). Thus, the ground of the Bakhtinian philosophy of communication is his vision of a conversation as an inter-exchange and enrichment of the dialogue participants as the owners of two different logics, two different sets of knowledge, two different philosophies, and two cultural backgrounds. At this point, Vygotsky's socio-cultural constructivism as co-constructing knowledge comes into play and fully supports Bakhtinian postulates.

Keywords: Bakhtin, classroom discourse, dialogue, co-constructing knowledge, polylogue